

MEDICAL SCIENCES

USING MEDICATED PASTE TO TEMPORARILY FILL ROOT CANALS

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Abstract

To study the effectiveness of using a medicinal composition for the treatment of chronic periodontitis. The results were assessed based on clinical examination and radiographic examination. Results. The data obtained as a result of a clinical study indicate the high effectiveness of the therapeutic composition as an antimicrobial agent and a means for stimulating bone tissue regeneration.

Keywords: Endodontic treatment, medicinal paste for filling root canals

There is a very great need among the population for endodontic treatment of complications of caries, pulpitis and periodontitis [1, 2]. This is caused by the significant prevalence of caries complications [3, 4]. Today, dentists have at their disposal almost all the various instruments and medications for endodontic treatment. However, analysis of literature data shows that the effectiveness of endodontic treatment is extremely low and does not exceed 20% [5, 6]. This is explained by the insufficiently correct use of instruments and the stages of treatment, in particular, insufficient treatment of root canals and their poor-quality filling [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of endodontic dental treatment is to prevent the occurrence of errors and complications, which, according to various authors, range from 30 to 70% [12, 13]. Typically, the root canal is filled within the apical narrowing, and the restoration of periapical tissues occurs due to the body's own defenses [14, 15, 16]. It is relevant to use medications for the treatment of chronic periodontitis to stimulate reparative processes in periapical tissues. For this purpose, it is proposed to use agents that have a pronounced osteoinductive effect: autologous materials, osteoplastic materials, etc. [17, 18]. Therefore, it is important to create complex medications that would have an antibacterial, anti-inflammatory effect and stimulate the regeneration of tissue in the periapical area. Many authors point out the inappropriateness of using antibiotics, amides, hormones, and phenolic drugs for this purpose, since the microflora quickly gets used to them and these drugs inhibit local tissue immunity and proliferation processes in tissues [19, 20, 21, 22]. The use of other, more effective drugs will increase the effectiveness of treatment of chronic periodontitis such as thiotriazolol and clipdent-gl. This mixture of drugs was mixed in a selected composition extempore to the consistency of a paste. The purpose of

the work was to clinically study the effectiveness of using the proposed therapeutic composition for temporary filling of root canals in the treatment of chronic periodontitis.

Materials and research methods

This study was conducted in a group of 26 patients with chronic periodontitis (10 with chronic granulating and 16 with chronic granulomatous periodontitis). The root canals of teeth with chronic periodontitis were treated instrumentally, always opening the apical foramen within no more than 0.2 mm. The canals were treated with medication and subsequently dried using paper points. On a glass plate or disposable sheets of paper notepad, the components of the proposed medicinal paste (metronidazole, thiotriazolol, clipdent-gl) were mixed to the consistency of a liquid paste. Using a root needle or canal filler, this medicinal composition was injected into the root canal. Through the open apical foramen, the components of the paste penetrated into the periodontal and periapical tissues and had a therapeutic effect on them. The tooth cavity was closed with a sealed bandage made of artificial dentin. If radiographs revealed a larger defect in the bone tissue of the periapical area, or if the anamnesis revealed that the root canal had been open for a long period of time, then the treatment tactics were slightly changed. After thorough instrumental and medicinal treatment of the root canal during the first visit, this medicinal composition was not used in the form of a paste, but was introduced into the root canal on a turunda. To do this, equal amounts of metronidazole and thiotriazolol were mixed on a glass plate or on a paper sheet. Then, Clipdent-GL granules were gradually added to the mixed solution until a rich white solution was formed. They impregnated a cotton swab, which was inserted into the root canal of the tooth. A few days later, if there were no complaints from the patient, the hermetic bandage was removed, the paste was removed from the root

canal, and the root canal was washed and dried. The root canal was permanently filled with AN+ material. At the same time, no attempt was made to move the filling material beyond the apical foramen into the periapical tissues. The quality of filling was controlled using x-rays. The carious cavity was closed with a temporary filling made of artificial dentin. If there were no patient complaints, a few days later the carious cavity of the tooth was permanently filled with a composite material. The effectiveness of treatment was assessed based on clinical and radiological data. The results were considered positive if they were characterized by the absence of patient complaints, changes in the condition of the gums, and restoration of bone tissue as specified in the X-ray examination for granulomatous and granulomatous periodontitis. Results and discussion Using this method, 26 teeth with chronic periodontitis were treated (10 and 16 with chronic granulomatous periodontitis). To control the treatment, intraoral contact radiography was used, which was used to determine the degree of filling of the root canals after filling them. There were no cases of exacerbation of the pathological process when there was a need to remove the hermetic dressing. In all cases of treatment, the root canals were filled completely; the filling mass after filling was not carried beyond the apex of the tooth (Fig.). In 2 teeth of the patients, minor pain was noted after filling the root canal, which quickly disappeared after 3-4 sessions of UHF therapy. In general, the treated teeth were painless upon percussion, functioned effectively when chewing, the mucous membrane around the teeth was without pathological changes. The tooth cavity was closed with a sealed bandage made of artificial dentin. Radiographs six months after treatment showed a decrease in the size of the pathological lesion in the periapical tissues. Complete filling of the root canals allows them to be effectively obturated and contributes to the absence of significant irritation of the periapical tissues. The medications used for treatment do not irritate the periodontium. The results obtained indicate the high effectiveness of the clinical use of the proposed composition of drugs in the treatment of chronic periodontitis.

Conclusions.

This gives grounds to recommend this therapeutic composition for the treatment of chronic periodontitis.

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